

Deliverable 4.3.2

LIST OF METADATA STANDARDS AND RELEVANCE FOR NFDI4ENERGY
10.11.2025

List of Metadata Standards and Relevance for NFDI4Energy

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General Information

Summary

This deliverable represents a large survey of metadata standards from multiple sources and puts them in context for NFDI4Energy. Metadata standards are categorized by their relevance for energy research data from not relevant, over partially relevant to relevant or even important. The relevant and important standards are further categorized in what kind of standard they represent. We distinguish classical online catalog metadata standards, metadata toolkits, and domain specific metadata standards that focus on a very specific kind of data. The goal of this deliverable is threefold: First, to clarify what the expectations for an NFDI4Energy service are, when they handle energy research data. This explicitly means that we expect the support of the Open Energy Metadata Standard, as the primary domain specific Metadata Standard for energy research data. Second, to serve as a guideline for researchers in the energy domain on what metadata standards to use and lastly to be a lookup table for solution ideas on how to solve several metadata challenges or specific modeling solutions for domain specific metadata. The latter is achieved by listing the partially relevant metadata standards and by providing a link to the respective registries of metadata standards for each mentioned standard.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

In NFDI4Energy Task Area 4 is tasked with the creation and curation of ontologies and metadata standards. Measure 4.3 is tasked with collecting requirements and developing the metadata standards that shall be used for energy research data in NFDI4Energy. To do so, it is necessary to understand the existing metadata standards and evaluate their applicability. This falls under task 4.3.2, which contains two subtasks that are completed through this deliverable: First 4.3.2.1 is the collection of a list of metadata standards, which is the foundation on which this deliverable is built. And second 4.3.2.2 the evaluation of the concepts and technical makeup of all the standards with regard to applicability in energy research.

Furthermore, this deliverable defines a guideline for services that handle energy research data, and therefore it also affects task area 8 which focuses on services in NFDI4Energy.

Review of existing metadata standards

Metadata have their origin in the libraries of ancient times. They have been used to manage large collections of documents to be able to find a specific item. The name “Metadata” was coined by Philip Bagley in 1968, originally to describe data types for programming languages, but was then used to describe physical and digital objects soon thereafter.

Over the past decades many “Metadata Standards” have been created as a collection of guidelines, formats and schemas for the description of assets. Many of them are very specific for a certain kind of asset while others aim to be as generic as possible to be used for as many assets as possible. Moreover, some of them are already quite old, some have been superseded by newer ones, while there are still newcomers frequently.

In Measure 4.3 we have created a review of many Metadata Standards and evaluated their usefulness for the energy domain. This is primarily based on the Research Data Alliance (RDA) metadata standards catalog¹ and the standards section of FAIRsharing.org². All metadata standards have initially been categorized like this:

- Non-relevant standards
- Contains interesting technical concepts
- Contains relevant content for the energy domain
- Relevant for the energy domain
- Important for the energy domain

This classification has been done based on a quick review of the standard, and for the last two categories a more detailed analysis was performed. This analysis will be described in more detail later on.

Classification of different types of standards

A second kind of classification that we have done (at least for the standards that we considered relevant) is about the properties and field of application of the standard at hand. Not all standards have been designed to do exactly the same thing, so it is obvious that their focus may be on a different use-case or field of application.

We have tried to group similar standards and we ended up with the following three categories of standards:

Classical Online Data Catalog Metadata Standard

The first group focuses on publishing use cases and the management of many assets in a collection. It can be considered the traditional metadata standard as also the ancient libraries might have used something like this. Further goals of these kind of standards are discoverability and catalog entry standardization across different kinds of assets. As a result those standards will usually not have any domain-specific details about an asset. The common representatives of this group for NFDI4Energy are DCAT, DataCite, and Dublin Core.

Metadata Handling Toolkits

This group focuses on tools that help with tasks that are necessary along the metadata life cycle. This includes for example the handling of multiple file or data formats, such that they can be parsed and understood by machines and humans alike. Further application areas might be the transport and validation of metadata, as well as the bundling of metadata alongside the data. Typical representatives of this category are Data Package, Research Object Crate (RO-Crate), and Provenance Document Collection (PROV).

¹<https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/>

²<https://FAIRsharing.org/standards>

Domain Specific Metadata Standards

This last group contains specialized standards that are tailored to particular domains and focus on details of specific use cases. They can also often be controlled by regulatory measures. For NFDI4Energy the representatives are for example International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 19115, Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe (INSPIRE), and our dedicated energy related metadata standard Open Energy Metadata (OEMetadata).

List of non-relevant metadata standards

The following lists of metadata standards, have been classified as non-relevant for NFDI4Energy. This can have several causes:

- The standard was replaced by a newer one
- The standard focuses only on a specific topic that is not related to energy
- The standard is no longer maintained
- There is no proper schema or documentation available online
- There has been no notable content that is not covered by more important standards

Table 1 and Table 2 are displayed in a two column layout, and the actual table also has two columns: The title of the metadata standard and an identifier. The identifier is written in Compact Uniform Resource Identifier (CURIE) form and the used prefixes are *msc*: <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/msc/> and *fs*: <https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing..> You can use these URLs to resolve the entries in the previously mentioned metadata standards catalogs. There will be no further explanation of these metadata standards.

Standards that provide some benefits

The standards listed in this subsection can be classified into two groups: Either they are interesting because of technical concepts (e.g. a solution for controlled vocabularies) or they provide some interesting metadata fields that can be referenced for specific kinds of energy data sets (e.g. sensor configurations).

Technically relevant metadata standards

This category is not necessarily relevant for metadata users within the energy domain, but more focused on developers of metadata standards and tools.

Asset Description Metadata Schema (ADMS) (msc:m48)

ADMS is a DCAT profile designed for annotating metadata schemas, taxonomies, dictionaries, data models, and other semantic artifacts listed in data catalogs. In that sense it is interesting for NFDI4Energy to manage different relevant metadata standards and schemas.

Biolink Model (fs:ad9d85)

The Biolink Model is entirely implemented in LinkML and can be seen as a real world example on how to use this technology for schema definition and management.

Bioschemas ComputationalTool Profile (fs:991d4e)

Bioschemas heavily utilizes Schema.org to create their models. It can be seen as an example on how to create domain specific models using schema.org concepts.

Name	ID	Name	ID
4DN-BINA-OME Microscopy Metadata Specifications	fs:87756d	Dryad Metadata Application Profile	msc:m55
ABCD	msc:m1	DwC Germplasm	msc:m56
ABCD Zoology	msc:m110	EAD	msc:m96
ABCDDNA	msc:m42	eBank UK Metadata Application Profile	msc:m57
ABCDEFG	msc:m43	EDMED Metadata Profile	msc:m58
Adaptive Immune Receptor Repertoire Standard	fs:eZ0fzl	EML	msc:m16
AGLS Metadata Profile	msc:m44	EURISCO Descriptors	msc:m85
AgMES	msc:m2	FAIRtracks	fs:807b9d
AGRIS Application Profile	msc:m45	FGDC/CSDGM	msc:m17
ANZLIC Metadata Profile	msc:m46	FGDC/CSDGM Biological Data Profile	msc:m59
Apple Core	msc:m47	FHIR	msc:m103
AVM	msc:m3	FITS	msc:m18
BIDS	msc:m113	FITS World Coordinate System (WCS)	msc:m60
CARARE Metadata Schema	msc:49	GBIF Metadata Profile	msc:m61
CESSDA CMM	msc:m50	Gene Ontology (GO) Gene Association File Format 2.2	fs:77fbbf
CESSDA Data Catalogue DDI Profiles	msc:m121	Genome Metadata	msc:m19
CF Metadata Conventions	msc:m5	GGBN Data Standard	
CIDOC CRM	msc:m114	HISPID	msc:m64
CIF	msc:m6	International HLA and Immunogenetics Workshop XML	fs:37nbt
CIM	msc:m7	ISA-JSON	fs:yhLgTV
COARDS Conventions	msc:m51	ISA-Tab	msc:m21
CRMarchaeo	msc:m118	ISA-TAB Nano	msc:m67
CRMdig	msc:m116	isaconfig-diXa	msc:m68
CRMsci	msc:m115	ISO 19115 North American Profile	msc:m70
CRMtex	msc:m119	ISO 28500:2017 Information and documentation — Web ARChive file format	fs:zl0vGD
Cruise Summary Reports	msc:m52		
Darwin Core Geospatial Extension	msc:m54		
Data Standard for Sharing Quantitative Results in Mass Spectrometry Metabolomics	fs:207caf		

Table 1: Non-relevant metadata standards for NFDI4Energy - Part 1

Center for Expanded Data Annotation and Retrieval (CEDAR) Template Model (msc:m94)
Originally designed for biomedical experiment data, CEDAR defines templates of metadata fields required for different types of experiments. A similar approach could be used to streamline the creation of metadata for different types of energy system experiments.

Common Data Format (fs:a4df96)

The Common Data Format is not a metadata schema, but rather a data format that combines the storage of data and metadata alongside each other. It also specializes in multi-dimensional data sets which is also of relevance in the energy domain.

Darwin Core (msc:m9)

Darwin Core stands out as a great example of interlinked standards. It is part of the Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) standard collection that contains many standards and vocabularies

Name	ID	Name	ID
LIDO	msc:m109	Open Modeling EXchange format	fs:27tnee
MAGE-TAB	msc:m87	openPMD	msc:m107
MARC	msc:m88	PDBx/mmCIF	msc:m30
Marine Community Profile	msc:m71	PICA XML	fs:9a67d2
MBF Bioscience Neuromorphological File Format 4.0	fs:ac3ea3	Plasma-MDS	msc:m105
MEDIN discovery metadata standard	msc:m123	PREMIS	msc:m31
Metabolomics Workbench Tabular File Format	fs:N8KDKt	Protocol Data Element Definitions	msc:m32
MIBBI	msc:m23	QuDEx	msc:m34
MIBBI Portal	msc:m72	RDA	msc:m104
MIDAS-Heritage	msc:m24	REMBI	msc:m112
Minimum Information about an Uncultivated Virus Genome	fs:bd9566	Repository-Developed Metadata Schemas	msc:m36
MIxS	msc:m108	Resource Metadata for the Virtual Observatory	msc:m74
MODS	msc:m97	RIF-CS	msc:m98
NBO-Q	msc:m111	RIOXX Metadata Application Profile	fs:40d902
NetCDF Attribute Convention for Dataset Discovery	msc:m89	SDAC	msc:m37
Neuroscience Information Exchange Format	fs:kK7dbW	Shoreline Metadata Profile	msc:m75
NeXus	msc:m25	smartAPI specification	fs:f3jewy
Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Markup Language	fs:es03fk	SNRNASM ISA-Tab	msc:m76
OAI-ORE	msc:m26	Standard for Documentation of Astronomical Catalogues	fs:zcjkc7
OBO Flat File Format Syntax and Semantics	fs:aa0eat	TEI Guidelines	msc:m99
Observ-OM	msc:m27	TEI/EPIDOC	msc:m120
ODM	msc:m106	TIDCC	msc:m78
OECD Dataset Metadata	msc:m90	The Core Metadata Schema for Learner Corpora	fs:987836
OECD Minimum Data Set	msc:m91	Time Frequency Catalogue	fs:cb4ca0
OME-XML	msc:m29	UK AGMAP	msc:m79
OpenAIRE Guidelines	msc:m92	UK Gemini	msc:m80
Open Microscopy Environment Next Generation File Formats	fs:9af712	UKEOF	msc:m40
		VarioML	msc:m82
		WMO Core Metadata Profile	msc:m84

Table 2: Non-relevant metadata standards for NFDI4Energy - Part 2

from the Biodiversity Domain. Most of those standards are built up using the same technical principles and are hosted centrally.

International DOI Foundation (IDF) Metadata Kernel (msc:m86)

This metadata kernel defines the possible information that can be placed directly into a DOI record. This is going to be interesting for any kind of data publications as it might enable linking directly to more detailed metadata.

International Virtual Observatory Alliance (IVOA) Technical Specifications (msc:m20)

The technical specifications of the IVOA are a collection of vocabularies and schemas that are maintained and version controlled individually. It forms a large collection of metadata modules for tele-

scope data. It can serve as a technical example on how to work with many individually versioned schemas that together form meaningful metadata.

Open Microscopy Environment TIFF (OME-TIFF) (msc:m73)

This standard shows how to integrate Open Microscopy Environment XML (OME-XML) metadata in Tagged Image File Format (TIFF) image files. Although images are not of the most importance in the energy domain now, it might be an interesting technical starting point if this is necessary for a specific use case.

Content-wise relevant metadata standards

This category can provide some insight on metadata standards on various types of data that are relevant for the energy domain.

Allgemeines Metadatenprofil für Bildungsressourcen (AMB) (msc:m126)

This standard - in English, the *General Metadata Profile for Educational Resources* - aligns with the NFDI4Energy Best Practices Service and may be of use in cataloging the metadata of the tutorials and other learning resources that will be shared in this service.

Bioschemas Training Material (fs:fd7e23)

This small metadata schema handles the description of training material that could be reused accordingly for the energy domain.

CodeMeta (fs:TS3gpY)

CodeMeta³ is a metadata standard for research software [1]. Originating from collaborations within the working groups of FORCE11, WSSPE and the Software Sustainability Institute. CodeMeta was first released in 2017 and it establishes a concept vocabulary that enables the standardized exchange of software metadata across repositories and organizations such as GitHub, Zenodo and DataCite. Research software is an overarching topic that is also relevant in the energy domain.

Common European Research Information Format (CERIF) (msc:m4)

This standard is designed to capture metadata about research projects, such as the involved institutions and the funding sources. It may be relevant for the NFDI4Energy Competence Service, which aims to connect researchers and support scientific collaboration.

Content Standard for Digital Geospatial Metadata (CSDGM) Extensions for Remote Sensing Metadata (msc:m53)

The standard has some fields for multi-band remote sensing instruments, extending on the digital geospatial metadata that might also be relevant for specific applications in the energy domain.

Core Scientific Metadata Model (CSMD) (msc:m8)

This standard defines the basic concepts of scientific work linking datasets, with investigations and necessary instruments. It further touches on the topics of parameters of a dataset or instrument, while being entirely modeled in Web Ontology Language (OWL).

CSV on the Web (CSVW) (msc:m125)

This standard[2] is maintained by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) and handles the annotation of tabular data.

³<https://codemeta.github.io/>

Directory Interchange Format (DIF) (msc:m14)

DIF is a well established standard for satellite data, that includes weather data, that could be relevant in the context of NFDI4Energy. It is maintained by NASA. However, the basic example could most likely be covered by one of the major metadata standards.

EngMeta (msc:m100)

EngMeta is a metadata standard for engineering simulations and supports automated metadata extraction. EngMeta provides a structured framework for describing technical data and design artifacts, supporting interoperability across engineering tools and platforms.

ERSMeta (not registered)

ERSMeta is a metadata standard for research software targeting the energy domain. NFDI4Energy actively influences its development. As mentioned before, research software is also of relevance in the energy domain.

Generic Statistical Message for Time Series (GESMES/TS) (msc:m62)

Standard from the finance sector for exchanging statistical information. This particular extension focuses on time series data that might also be relevant in the energy domain.

Generic Statistical Information Model (GSIM) (msc:m63)

GSIM is a standard of the United Nations to represent statistics and their variables. This might be helpful for long term scenarios and statistical energy experiments.

IMPEX Data Model (msc:m65)

This metadata standard does cover simulations of physical phenomena and might help to find common ground for simulations in the energy domain.

Library Reference Model (LRMoo) (msc:m117)

LRMoo is an extension of the International Committee on Documentation - Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC-CRM) and contains terminology for representing bibliographic information. While designed for libraries and museums, it could be repurposed for collections of scientific publications.

Metadata4Ing (fs:f8b3ec)

Metadata4Ing is more an ontology than an explicit metadata standard, though it provides important concepts to describe data generation processes in the engineering sciences, which is closely related to the energy domain.

Observations and Measurements (msc:m28)

Observations and Measurements is a standard that defines the conceptual model and Extensible Markup Language (XML) schema of observation results and their metadata, allowing consistent exchange of sensor data across diverse systems.

Open Data for Access and Mining (ODAM) Structural Metadata (msc:m127)

ODAM provides a model tabular data structures that look similar to the frictionless tabular data package, but is entirely redefined.

Resource Description Framework (RDF) Data Cube Vocabulary (msc:m35)

Maintained by the W3C, this standard tackles high-dimensional data, which is also sometimes relevant for energy applications.

Statistical Data and Metadata eXchange (SDMX) (msc:m38)

The coverage area of this standard is statistical data from social, demographic, and economic backgrounds, which can also be relevant for energy-domain questions.

Sensor Observation Service Interface Schema (SOS) (not registered)

SOS defines an XML schema for different kinds of sensor data, which can influence potential solutions for multilayer metadata for sensor data.

Simple Knowledge Organisation System (SKOS) (not registered)

SKOS is a terminology to build up taxonomies and thesauri which is helpful for creating controlled vocabularies.

Space Physics Archive Search and Extract (SPASE) Data Model (msc:m39)

This standard handles space observation data that could find an application in resilience studies based on extraterrestrial influences on the power grid. Furthermore, some parts target the subject of simulation.

US Geoscience Information Network (USGIN) Metadata Profile (msc:m81)

This is a framework for sharing geoscience data across different organizations. USGIN promotes the use of standardized metadata, such as International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 19115 and Dublin Core, and implements web services for access to distributed geoscience data repositories.

WaterML (msc:m83)

WaterML is an open standard information model for the representation and exchange of hydrological time series data.

Process of review for the relevant and important metadata standards

After the initial screening of metadata standards that delivered the initial classification, it was necessary to perform a more detailed analysis why the remaining standards are relevant or even important for NFDI4Energy and the energy domain in general.

The analysis includes the following categories:

- Core Data
 - Name
 - URL
 - Schema Type
 - Origin story
 - Current Version / History (first release)
 - Maintainer and Process
 - Classification of standard type (can be multiple)
- Usage
 - Description of standard and application field
 - Applicability towards different data classification types (e.g. from OEP)
 - Applicability for tabular data (common data structure)
 - A link to an example data set
 - What services and projects do use that standard?

- Integration and extensibility
 - Support for modularity?
 - Available support for developers to integrate standards
 - Referencing other standards?

Relevant metadata standards in the energy domain

The standards in this section are not primary recommendations for general use, but might be useful for certain parts of your metadata or to solve a specific use-case.

Component MetaData Infrastructure (CMDI) (msc:m122)

The CMDI⁴ is a standard that describes how to define metadata profiles for the Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure (CLARIN) environment [3]. The coordination of CMDI development is done by a dedicated task force within the Standing Committee for CLARIN Technical Centres (SCCTC). Version 1.2 of CMDI was released in 2014 [4].

CMDI provides a component-based and extensible model that allows users to build metadata profiles for specific data types. A CMDI record is an XML-based metadata file and it references reusable components defined in the CMDI component registry, thereby ensuring the structural and semantic consistency across resources.

CMDI is highly flexible in terms of supported metadata models, without prescribing any specific structure or terminology. Metadata models can be defined, reused and recombined through components and profiles within the CMDI framework.

Data Package (msc:m10)

Data Package [5] is a Java Script Object Notation (JSON)-based standard that provides simple and extensible specifications to describe datasets, data files, and tabular data. It is developed and maintained by the Frictionless Data Initiative. The first specification of Data Package was released in 2016, and the latest stable release was in 2024.

Data Package consists of two main parts, a metadata descriptor that defines the structure and contents, and the resources (e.g., data files) themselves. The Data Package specification imposes no restriction on the form or structure of the data and therefore makes it suitable for packing any type of data.

Data Package can be integrated with other metadata standards such as frictionless Table Schema, Research Object Crate (RO-Crate), DataCite and DCAT, allowing data exchange across platforms and infrastructures. The standard is highly extensible, and it provides a rich set of metadata and data features for general applications. Furthermore, it is domain-agnostic and does not include any metadata in specific knowledge domains. Therefore, domain-specific extensions can be used to enrich Data Package's metadata to meet the needs of a knowledge domain.

Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) (msc:m13)

The DDI is an international metadata standard that is considered to be the most advanced for describing both quantitative and qualitative research metadata in the social, behavioral, economic, and health sciences[6]. DDI is maintained by the DDI Alliance, an open membership organization, and the standard has developed several versions: DDI Codebook schema 2.x for documenting survey and microdata, DDI Lifecycle schema 3.x for modeling complex data workflows and relationships across the entire data life cycle, and the latest version, DDI Cross-Domain Integration (DDI-CDI) for improving the interoperability of research data. All those releases can be found on GitHub⁵.

Its structured, machine-actionable framework is XML-based, modular, and supports life cycle documentation from study design and data collection through processing, archiving, and reuse [7], [8]. DDI is also extended beyond only using XML, by being able to be represented as RDF through the DDI-RDF Discovery Vocabulary [9]. For NFDI4Energy, DDI is relevant because its detailed process documentation and its interoperability features provide a model for capturing heterogeneous energy datasets, ensuring reproducibility, transparency, and cross-domain integration.

⁴<https://www.clarin.eu/content/cmd-i-component-metadata-infrastructure>

⁵<https://github.com/ddialliance>

International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 19115 (msc:m22)

ISO 19115 [10] is an international standard and it defines how to describe geographic information and services through metadata. It provides a comprehensive metadata schema and is primarily encoded in XML (defined via ISO 19139 [11] or ISO 19115-3), but can also be represented in other machine-readable forms. It was first released in 2003 and has received several updates, extensions and amendments since then. The current active standards versions are ISO 19115-1:2014 with two amendments from 2018 and 2020, ISO 19115-2:2019 with an amendment from 2022, and ISO 19115-3:2023. The extensions 4 and 5 are currently in development. The standard can be classified as a domain specific metadata standard as it focuses on geographic data.

ISO 19115 is widely adopted by national mapping agencies, research institutions, and spatial data infrastructures. It is also highly relevant for many energy related datasets as a proper geographical setting can be important to understand them. An example of an ISO 19115 record can be found online ⁶.

The standard is referencing some other ISO standards but is not really interlinked with many of the classical metadata standards. Implementation support for developers exists from some community projects like GeoNetwork ⁷.

Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe (INSPIRE) (msc:m66)

INSPIRE is a European directive that defines a metadata standard based on ISO 19115/19139 (international geospatial standards) [12] and also aligns it with regulations and processes. Its purpose is to create a harmonized spatial data infrastructure across Europe, enabling better environmental policies and cross-border data sharing. It was first passed in 2007 and institutions throughout Europe have been required to adopt it in the following years. It also qualifies as a domain specific standard as it is all about geospatial information.

Provenance Document Collection (PROV) (msc:m33)

The W3C PROV standard defines a model and set of documents for representing provenance, i.e., information about origin, history, and processing of data [13]. It is published as an OWL ontology with the prefix `http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#`. It is also available as an XML schema. PROV was developed by the W3C to provide a means to solve the requirements brought up by the provenance incubator group and was first released in 2012. The current version dates to 2013. It can be classified as a domain specific metadata standard as it focuses on the life cycle of data sets.

PROV is a structured set of provenance descriptions that can capture how datasets were created, transformed, combined, or used. Therefore, it has three core concepts: Entities, Activities, and Agents. It also describes several properties to connect those three core concepts. An example can be found as part of the documentation ⁸. In the context of NFDI4Energy, PROV can help capture and systematically document how raw measurements, simulations, and analyses are created and transformed, thereby supporting the reproducibility of complex energy system research. It is already widely used among many different research domains and online data platforms.

For developers, there are several language implementations that can be used to integrate the PROV standard. Moreover, PROV can be extended by further statements to give more detailed information on the evolution of an Entity. It is not referencing any other larger metadata standards, but acts as a generic solution that can be combined with any other metadata standard instead.

⁶https://docs.ogc.org/per/16-062.html#_c_1_example_iso_19139_listing

⁷<https://github.com/geonetwork/core-geonetwork>

⁸<https://www.w3.org/TR/2013/REC-prov-o-20130430/#narrative-example-simple-1>

Research Object Crate (RO-Crate) (msc:m102)

RO-Crate is a community driven metadata standard designed to describe research data, software, and workflows in a structured and machine-readable way [14]. It was first released in 2019 and the current version is 1.2 [15]. RO-Crate is encoded as a flattened and compacted Java Script Object Notation - Linked Data (JSON-LD) and builds on Schema.org as a metadata standard - with some small exceptions. So validation has to be done against the schema.org schema files. RO-Crate can be considered a metadata handling toolkit.

RO-Crates are used for many data artifacts that are published online and can even contain software to represent executable data objects. There are no real limitations on what kind of data can be wrapped into a RO-Crate so it also works for example with tabular data, though one will need an additional piece of metadata to describe the columns accordingly. An example file can be found in the documentation ⁹.

Developers can use a variety of software packages and tools that help with the integration of RO-Crates in various languages. As already mentioned, RO-Crate uses the Schema.org vocabulary so it is dependant on it but no other standards. There is no real support for modular metadata as it must follow Schema.org.

⁹<https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/specification/1.2/appendix/jsonld.html>

Most important metadata standards in the energy domain

This section covers the go-to standards if you intend to publish energy related data.

Open Energy Metadata (OEMetadata) (msc:m128)

The OEMetadata standard [16] has been established as the metadata standard for the Open Energy Platform (OEP) to annotate the datasets that are stored there. The first version available on GitHub was released in November 2019 and has since developed further to reach version 2.0.4 in March 2025. It is developed and maintained by the Reiner Lemoine Institute (RLI) and Open Energy Family Community. NFDI4Energy is also actively contributing to its development and has selected OEMetadata to be the primary metadata standard for data in the energy domain. It is published on GitHub to allow for issue tracking and continuous access to the past versions of the standard as well. The standard schema is available as a JSON schema¹⁰. It can be classified as a energy domain specific metadata standard.

A representative example¹¹ of a metadata record can be found directly on GitHub along with the documentation of the standard. The OEMetadata has been built on top of the Frictionless Data Package standard, which is well suited for annotating tabular data that is the main data type within the OEP. Projects that have published data on the Open Energy Platform using the OEMetadata standard include SIROP, open_FRED, open_MODEX, SzenarienDB, LOD-GEOSS and open_eGo. More details can be found on the OEP homepage¹². As OEMetadata is the only real domain specific metadata standard for the energy domain, its use has extended beyond the OEP to other data publications.

The standard currently aims to become more modular to allow for precise metadata records depending on the type and usage of the annotated data set. Developers can integrate the standard in their applications in form of the JSON schema. It references several other standards and ontologies like Dublin Core, DCAT, DBpedia Ontology (DBO), ADMS, Friend of a Friend Ontology (FOAF), National Cancer Institute Thesaurus (NCIT), Common Core Ontology (CCO), Software Package Data Exchange (SPDX), CSVW, PROV, Schema.org and of course the Open Energy Ontology (OEO).

DataCite (msc:m11)

The DataCite Metadata Schema [17] is managed by the Metadata Working Group of the DataCite community. The oldest available release, version 2.0, dates back to January 2011; currently, version 4.6 from December 2024 is the most recent update¹³. This schema is designed to be broadly applicable to research resources from a variety of domains, and is intended to be used in combination with other domain-specific metadata schemas whenever such a combination is necessary to fully describe a resource.

The DataCite schema is published in XML format, with a JSON mapping available. It contains 20 major properties, each defined as either Mandatory (6 properties), Recommended (6 properties), or Optional (8 properties). Most of the major properties are extended with sub-properties that allow for more detailed metadata specification.

In addition to the metadata schema, the maintainers publish mappings from DataCite's schema to other existing schemas. Usage examples, both demonstration cases and live usages, can be found in the schema's documentation. These resources greatly improve the usability and interoperability of this metadata schema.

¹⁰<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oemetadata/blob/production/oemetadata/latest/schema.json>

¹¹<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oemetadata/blob/v2.0.4/oemetadata/v2/v20/example.json>

¹²<https://openenergyplatform.org/about/>

¹³<https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.6/>

DataID (not registered)

The DataID ontology[18] is a multilayer ontology that consists of a core ontology and several extensions. It is developed on GitHub¹⁴ by a team at the University of Leipzig and uses the prefix url <http://dataid.dbpedia.org/ns/core#> for the core ontology (exchanging the *core* suffix for the extension modules as necessary). The ontology is available in both Terse RDF Triple Language (Turtle) and OWL formats. It was designed as a generic metadata structure for the DBPedia data set and was later used as the general metadata of the DBPedia Databus. The first release happened in 2014 and received several updates in the following years, although there seems to be no clear versioning scheme. It can be considered to be a Classical Online Data Catalog Metadata Standard.

The standard is primarily used for datasets that are registered on the DBPedia Databus. An automatic export from the Open Energy Platform (OEP) towards the Databus exists and it performs an automatic conversion of metadata from the Open Energy Metadata (OEMetadata) to DataID.

The metadata standard is by design modular as it uses the multilayer ontology to be extensible with further domain specific modules. There is no direct support for developers to integrate the standard directly and one has to start of with the published ontology files. It does reuse other standards like Dublin Core and DCAT for terms used in the ontology.

Dublin Core (msc:m15)

Dublin Core is a widely used metadata standard, initially developed in 1995 and released in 1998, and currently maintained by the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI). The latest version was released in January 2020. It aims to increase the interoperability of the Semantic Web and Linked Data principles by utilizing Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs) for both metadata and vocabularies. The Dublin Core consists of fifteen generic elements: Creator, Contributor, Publisher, Title, Date, Language, Format, Subject, Description, Identifier, Relation, Source, Type, Coverage, and Rights. This provides a flexible resource across nearly all disciplines, available in both RDF and XML formats. While it is intentionally designed for a generic purpose, it still allows for extensions with other metadata standards, especially in specialized domains such as biomedical data, and supports crosswalks and mappings to other metadata standards, thereby enhancing interoperability and exchange across systems.

Schema.org (msc:m101)

Schema.org is an online schema catalog that was created by a collaboration of several big tech companies, but has evolved into a broad community effort on the web. The first release dates back to 2011 and has reached version 29.2 on May 13 2025. The schema is published in several serializations. All the formats use semantic web technologies and are either based on Resource Description Framework Schema (RDFS) or OWL.

The main usage area is to provide semantic and structured data in any aspect of the web. That includes websites, emails, and any app that uses web technologies. As its focus area lies on information on the web, it can be utilized to describe many things on a broader level and often lacks the details to describe domain specific data sets like time series data. For example, a table is available in Schema.org as a table on a website that is expressed in Hypertext Markup Language (HTML). It therefore lacks the properties to give detailed descriptions on the data contained within the table, as it is considered a `WebPageElement` which is a `CreativeWork`. Example data can often be found on web pages e.g. on the BBC Homepage. Schema.org is widely used across industry and science and has impacted many other developments.

Modularity in the sense of giving guidance which properties or subclasses are relevant for a specific dataset is not handled by schema.org. Neither is it referencing other metadata standards. Many common values like the author of a creative work do not reuse the URLs of other standards. However, the RDA [19] and the W3C [20] have published crosswalks for important properties to other metadata

¹⁴<https://github.com/dbpedia/DataId-Ontology/tree/master>

standards. For developers, there is a dedicated guide¹⁵, but that focuses more on the availability of the schema in different formats rather than what to actually do with it.

Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) and Data Catalog Vocabulary - Application Profile (DCAT-AP) (msc:m12) and (msc:m124)

DCAT is an RDF vocabulary published as a recommendation by the W3C [21]. It provides a common framework for datasets and data catalogs to describe and expose their metadata. Initially, it was developed at the Digital Enterprise Research Institute (DERI), the version 1.0 [22] of the W3C recommendation was released in 2014 and version 3.0 in 2024 [21]. It is maintained by the Dataset Exchange Working Group (DXWG)¹⁶.

DCAT-AP is an application profile of the DCAT vocabulary aiming to enhance the semantic interoperability across European data portals [23]. It was developed in parallel to DCAT and version 1.0 was released in 2013 and version 3.0 in 2024. The maintenance of DCAT-AP is done by the DCAT-AP Working Group [24]. DCAT and DCAT-AP can both be classified as Classical Online Data Catalog Metadata Standards.

Different extensions of DCAT exist, like the already described DCAT-AP for governmental data, but also versions for governmental data in the USA [25] and many other countries exist, and more specific extensions have been created for example in the statistical and geodata domains. DCAT-AP can also be used with data spaces [26]. In the documentation of DCAT an example is provided showing how to represent a government catalog and its datasets¹⁷ and for DCAT-AP the use of dataset series is shown¹⁸. DCAT is used for different governmental data portals (e.g., <https://data.gov> in the USA) and also in different German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) consortia [27] like for example HealthDCAT-AP [26].

DCAT makes extensive use of terms from other vocabularies. Especially, Dublin Core is used, but also others like PROV Ontology (PROV-O) [28], ADMS, FOAF, SKOS, SPDX, Schema.org, and more are used or mapped.

¹⁵<https://schema.org/docs/developers.html>

¹⁶https://www.w3.org/2017/dxwg/wiki/Main_Page

¹⁷<https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/#basic-example>

¹⁸<https://semiceu.github.io/DCAT-AP/releases/3.0.0/#example-dataset-series>

Conclusion and Recommendations

When you want to publish your data as an energy researcher, you will have to choose a publication platform. There are several valid options available, but they are not discussed in this deliverable. It is almost certain that the platform will have its own set of mandatory metadata which can be based on a certain metadata standard. Traditionally, this will be one of the classical data catalog standards like DCAT-AP, DataCite or Schema.org. These three standards are also the three general standards that are recommended by the NFDI [27] and should be supported by any NFDI associated service. So, there is not really much choice in that regard. However, the interesting part for future use-cases will be the use of domain specific metadata standards, as they enable proper search of existing datasets for a certain purpose.

So we generally encourage energy researchers to pick a domain specific metadata standard and at least publish that metadata alongside their actual data (e.g. as a sidecar file).

At the moment, the Open Energy Metadata (OEMetadata) Standard is the primary NFDI4Energy recommendation for both services and researchers for energy research data. The Standard is the only real energy domain specific metadata standard and has been actively developed to fulfill the requirements that have previously been published by measure 4.3 [29]. NFDI4Energy actively participates in its further development to achieve full compliance with the defined requirements.

NFDI4Energy is currently working on solutions for domain metadata aware search that can actually harness this information. Furthermore, there will be a community space to modify existing standards to better suit researcher needs, which might end up being adopted by the community in general.

This deliverable has provided an overview of many existing metadata standards and serves as an initial guide to choose the right standard for metadata that suits the use-cases of energy researchers and service providers.

Glossary

ADMS	Asset Description Metadata Schema
AMB	Allgemeines Metadatenprofil für Bildungsressourcen
CCO	Common Core Ontology
CEDAR	Center for Expanded Data Annotation and Retrieval
CERIF	Common European Research Information Format
CIDOC-CRM	International Committee on Documentation - Conceptual Reference Model
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CMDI	Component MetaData Infrastructure
CSDGM	Content Standard for Digital Geospatial Metadata
CSMD	Core Scientific Metadata Model
CSVW	CSV on the Web
CURIE	Compact Uniform Resource Identifier
DBO	DBpedia Ontology
DCAT-AP	Data Catalog Vocabulary - Application Profile
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DCMI	Dublin Core Metadata Initiative
DDI-CDI	DDI Cross-Domain Integration
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DERI	Digital Enterprise Research Institute
DIF	Directory Interchange Format
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DXWG	Dataset Exchange Working Group
FOAF	Friend of a Friend Ontology
FORCE11	Future of Research Communication and e-Scholarship Community
GESMES/TS	Generic Statistical Message for Time Series
GSIM	Generic Statistical Information Model
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
IDF	International DOI Foundation
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IVOA	International Virtual Observatory Alliance
JSON-LD	Java Script Object Notation - Linked Data
JSON	Java Script Object Notation
LRM_{oo}	Library Reference Model
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NCIT	National Cancer Institute Thesaurus
NFDI	German National Research Data Infrastructure
ODAM	Open Data for Access and Mining
OEMetadata	Open Energy Metadata
OEO	Open Energy Ontology
OEP	Open Energy Platform
OME-TIFF	Open Microscopy Environment TIFF
OME-XML	Open Microscopy Environment XML
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PROV	Provenance Document Collection
PROV-O	PROV Ontology
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDFS	Resource Description Framework Schema
RLI	Reiner Lemoine Institute

RO-Crate	Research Object Crate
SCCTC	Standing Committee for CLARIN Technical Centres
SDMX	Statistical Data and Metadata eXchange
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organisation System
SPASE	Space Physics Archive Search and Extract
SPDX	Software Package Data Exchange
SOS	Sensor Observation Service Interface Schema
TIFF	Tagged Image File Format
TDWG	Biodiversity Information Standards
Turtle	Terse RDF Triple Language
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
USGIN	US Geoscience Information Network
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WSSSPE	Working Towards Sustainable Software for Science: Practice and Experiences
XML	Extensible Markup Language

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